

USING ICT BASED RESOURCES AND SERVICES OF AMONG UG STUDENTS, PG STUDENTS AND FACULTY MEMBERS OF AKOLA DISTRICTS LIBRARY

Dr Hemchandra Laxman Sasane, Assistant Professor Department of Education, Mahatma Gandhi Antarrashtriya Hindi Vishwavidyalaya WARDHA MAHARASHTRA

Abstract:

This study has been undertaken to Using ICT based resources and services of among UG students, PG students and faculty members of Akola districts library.. The study was performed via a questionnaire survey of the library users. The papers also determine users regarding Updating knowledge, Reading newspaper by the users in libraries.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology (ICT), ICT based resources and services

Introduction

Library is a fast growing organization, the ancient methods of maintaining it are no longer dynamic and efficient for expeditions, retrieval and dissemination of information and better service for the students; application of modern techniques has become absolutely indispensable. A properly computerized library will help its students with quick and prompt services. A digital library is an automated or electronic library where activities like accessing; with the help of a computer does resource sharing and storing. The university library is that kind of library situated in higher institution of learning, more specifically a university institution. Madu (2004) defined the university library as "one attached to an institution of higher learning of the status of a university and that it serves primarily students, staff and others who need its services. Because the university library is established to support the objectives of the university which is to promote teaching, learning and research, it is imperative that it serves the undergraduate, postgraduate, lecturers and other members of the university community.

For undergraduate students, the library is expected to provide information materials and services specially structured for their academic pursuit. For postgraduate students, teaching staff and research fellows, the university library is strategic in providing information resources and services of depth quality. That is why Agboola (2005) posit that university libraries are very important components of university institutions. He further argued that no university can lay claim to academic excellence without a good library to back up its teaching, research and public service mandates. Similarly, the quality of a university is measured largely by the quality of its library. Thus, because of the strategic place the library occupies in the university system, no university can function effectively without it.

Importantly, Libraries cannot exist as a single entity and technology to link their resources, the collections of these digital libraries are not limited to surrogate development but extend further to digital artifacts that cannot be represented or distributed in printed formats. Digital libraries are a shift in electronic content; this enables libraries to apply a growing range of information technology to the management of collection of print information. The emergence of the World Wide Web is perhaps the great symbol to this shift with all applications for scholarly communication, raise of the computationally science, the new role of databases. The term "e-library" refers to information accessed through the Internet. Unlike traditional libraries, e-libraries are not limited by location or time. Libraries have changed with the emergence and application of IT. They have assumed the role of educators, teaching users to find, evaluate, and use information both in the library and over electronic networks. As the use of e-library continues to soar, users are expected to develop information literacy skills. These skills, as Julien (2002) observes, will enable users to make efficient and effective use of information sources. Therefore, Information literacy is increasingly important (especially amongst students).

The application of ICT has drastically transformed the way of collection, storage and retrieval of information in libraries. Particularly, the internet has completely transformed the traditional libraries into digital libraries. Using the internet information may be accessed from anywhere of the universe.

The rapid development in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) provides tools such as computers, interactive multimedia CD-ROMs, e-mail and Internet, the use of such well- advances technologies has now enabled the learners of flexible learning to stimulate a virtual learning and take the mars to virtual campus wherein teacher learner interaction becomes possible in the cyberspace The flexible teaching leaning strategies provide high quality education and ensure equity in educational opportunities, particularly to the disadvantaged like physically challenged, adult learners etc.

Therefore, academic libraries are expected to serve the students, lecturers and other members of the academic community. To meet the information need of users, academic libraries provide various services such as user education (orientation/instruction services), inter-library loan/connection services, abstracting and indexing services, referral services and circulation services. Other services provided include library book loan, reference services, photocopying, online services, compilation of reading list and bibliographies, email, internet connectivity, CD-Researching and publishing(Ifidon, 2006)

Now-a-days, collection of library is not confined to physical boundaries that require the user to visit the library. Printed collections have become more expensive and not easily accessible to the users due to lack of time. The technological encroachments have led to tremendous changes in the process of information. In IT era, no library can encounter the requirements of users with printed sources of information. Today people use the information as a primary source of information. The internet can be used for efficient retrieval and meeting information needs. ICT based resources are now considered Asbeing of great importance to all types of libraries and they are reducing a large share of library budgets. They are used in abundance. These resources have solved the problem of space.

In the view of the above, the researcher intended to undertake this topic on study aims to ascertain the availability of ICT based resources and services, know about ICT based resources and services available in library, purpose of using ICT based resources and services, opinions about ICT based resources and services among UG students, PG students and faculty members of Akola districts.

Statement of the Problem

Using ICT based resources and services of among UG students, PG students and faculty members of Akola districts library.

Objectives

1. To find out the Frequency of library visit of using ICT based resources and services by respondents.
2. To find out the different purposes of using ICT based resources and services by respondents.

Methodology

The survey method has been used for the collection of data. The primary data has been collected with the help of a questionnaire. The basic purpose of the investigation was to determine the kind of library visit, ICT based resources and services library and its users. A questionnaire was sent to UG 40 students, PG 30 students and 30 faculty members of Akola districts college libraries.

Data Analysis

The questionnaires were coded after data collection. The data obtained were tabulated and analyzed using the statistical package for the Microsoft excel version 6. Hypotheses were tested and findings were drawn in the light of the objectives of the investigation.

Status wise distribution of respondents

Table 1.1. Status wise distribution of respondents

Distribution	UG Students	PG Students	Faculty Members	Total
Responded	40	30	30	100
Percentage	40	30	30	100

Table no 1.1 shows that The status wise distribution of respondents under the study is shown in Table 1.1 and figure1.1. It shows that out of 100 total respondents, 40 (40%) respondents are UG students, 30 (30%) respondents are PG students and the remaining 30 (30%) respondents are faculty members

Figure 1.1. Status wise distribution of respondents

How often users visited the library

Table 1.2. Frequency of library visit

Distribution	UG Students	PG Students	Faculty Members	Total
As and when needed	15	03	03	21
Daily	05	10	13	28
Once in a week	10	07	04	21
More than a week	05	06	06	17
Monthly	05	04	04	13
Total	40	30	30	100

Table no 1.2 shows that Data presented in table to the institution library. It could be noted that out of the total 100 respondents, 21 (21.00%) respondents are visit As and when needed,28 (28.00%) respondents are visit Daily 21(21.00%) respondents are visit Once in a week,17(17%) respondents are visit More than a week and 13 (13.00%) respondents are visit Monthly required.

Status wise purpose of library visit

Table 1.3. Status wise purpose of library visit

Purpose	UG Students	PG Students	Faculty Members	Total
Updating knowledge	18	12	10	40
For Circulation	02	02	10	14
Prepare for examination	10	04	02	16
For Browsing Internet	05	08	02	15
Reading newspaper	05	04	06	15
Total	40	30	30	100

Table no 1.3 shows that library visit. It can be seen from the table that total 100 respondents, 40 (40.00%) respondents are visit Updating knowledge needed, 14 (14.00%) respondents are visit For Circulation needed, 16 (16.00%) respondents are visit For Prepare for examination needed, 15 (15.00%) respondents are visit For Browsing Internet needed, 15 (15.00%) respondents are visit For Reading newspaper needed

References

1. A.A. Adeleke R. Olorunsola, (2010). "ICT and library operations". *The Electronic Library*, Vol. 28 (3), pp. 453-462.
2. Baruchson-Arbib, S., & Bronstein, J. (2004). "A view to the future of library and information profession : A Delphi study". *Journal of the American Society for Information Science And Technology*, 53, 397-408.
3. Dhanavandan, S. and Tamizhchelvan M. (2012). "Use Pattern of Digital Resources Among Engineering Colleges in Tamil Nadu, India". *International Journal of Library Science*,
4. Moorthy A.L. and Krisiddappa, C.R. (2001). "Information infrastructure and use of electronic media in Indian libraries". *Proceedings of the First South Indian Library Conference on Role of University and College Libraries in the Changing Information Scenario (Pooti Sreeramulu Telugu University, Hyderabad)*, p148-162.
5. Rajput (2007). "Internet Resources and Services in Institute of Engineering and Science". *IPS Academy Indore: An Exploratory Study. Library Progress (International)*, 27(2).

**International Journal of Cultural Studies
and Social Sciences**

ISSN : 2347 - 4777

CERTIFICATE OF PUBLICATION

This is to certify that the article entitled

**USING ICT BASED RESOURCES AND SERVICES OF AMONG UG STUDENTS, PG STUDENTS AND
FACULTY MEMBERS OF AKOLA DISTRICTS LIBRARY**

Authored By

Dr Hemchandra Laxman Sasane

Assistant Professor Department of Education, Mahatma Gandhi Antarrashtriy hindi Vishwavidhyalay
WARDHA MAHARASHTRA

Published in

International Journal of Cultural Studies and Social Sciences

ISSN 2347-4777 with IF=7.138

Vol-20, Issue-02, No.19, July - December: 2024

Double-Blind, Peer Reviewed, Refereed & Open Access, UGC CARE Listed Journal

